

Distributed Distance-based Formation-Motion Control of Unicycle Agents without Orientation Measurements

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Abstract—This paper presents a distance-based distributed control law to simultaneously reach a desired rigid formation shape and to reach a constant consensus velocity where the whole group moves in unison. The local control law in each agent uses only local relative positions defined in a local coordinate frame, without the need to measure the orientation of its neighbours nor to exchange local state information with the neighbors. Using transversally exponential stability analysis, we establish the local exponential convergence of the closed-loop systems to the desired formation shape and consensus group motion. Numerical simulations are presented to show the effectiveness of our proposed method.

Index Terms—Formation control, multiagent systems, distributed control

I. INTRODUCTION

Over the past decade, numerous research studies have been conducted on distributed formation control, due to its various problem setups and wide applications in robotics. Early works focus on the formation maintenance of point masses described by single integrators primarily [1]. In these works, the graph rigidity framework [2], [3], [4] has been used to define the formation shape and to design the corresponding distributed gradient-based control laws. This approach has become the basis for further development of distributed formation control with different sensing modalities, such as, distance-based formation control [5]–[8], bearing-only formation control [9], angle-based formation control [10], inner-angle based formation control and elevation-angle formation control [11]. For second-order agents, the design of formation control has been explored in [12], [13]. In general, formation control can be classified into two categories based on the way the coordinate is defined in the local control laws [14], namely, coordinate-based and coordinate-free methods. The coordinate-based formation control methods require a common knowledge of a global coordinate system, as seen in position-based methods, or they need the alignment of agents' coordinate frames, as

in the displacement-based and bearing-based methods. In contrast, the coordinate-free formation control define the desired shape by a set of coordinate-free variables (e.g., distances, angles), providing flexibility for agents to measure relative information in their local coordinate frame. Coordinate-free methods are attractive for applications as it eliminates the dependency on GPS for global position measurements or the need for an accurate compass to achieve coordinated orientation alignment.

Recently, with the increasing exploration of real-world application possibilities, there has been a growing focus on distributed formation control for agents with constraints [15], formation-motion problems [16] and those with distributed collision avoidance capability. While formation control methods for point-mass agents has reached certain maturity, their generalization to nonholonomic or under-actuated systems is still a work in progress [17], [18], [19]. Nonholonomic constraints are commonly encountered in wheeled mobile robotics, which brings motion restriction on the 2D plane. In this paper, we propose a new method to address coordinate-free formation control motion problem with the nonholonomic constraint of unicycle agents. Using the local coordinate frame aligned to the unicycle agent's orientation, our proposed approach is capable of simultaneously achieving the desired formation shape and ensuring orientation consistency.

The existing studies addressing formation shape control and orientation consistency can be broadly categorized into two main groups. In the first group, a leader-follower structure is employed with a directed spanning tree graph [19], [20]. In these methodologies, the leaders typically follow a predefined trajectory, while the followers estimate orientation or velocity information through observers. The state convergence of the followers is typically influenced by the state convergence of their leaders. In contrast, the formation problem addressed in this paper is based on an undirected rigid graph. This implies that each agent has no predefined trajectories, and their input is influenced by its neighbors. This introduces challenges in estimating the neighbors' state, presenting technical complexities in the formation control problem considered in this paper.

In another group, an undirected graph topology is considered, and the distributed control law is based on information exchange with conventional consensus methods [21]–[24]. These approaches primarily rely on two assumptions: either local coordinates are aligned (coordinate-based methods), or agents can sense orientation. These assumptions imply that

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orientation information can be measured directly or indirectly. However, achieving the alignment of local frames of coordinates or ensuring the availability of orientation measurements proves challenging in certain real-world scenarios. The alignment of local frames of coordinates typically requires additional sensors, such as GPS or a compass. Sensing orientation can also be challenging to execute, as the accuracy of orientation measurements is significantly affected by various factors, including raw sensor data, such as the point cloud from a LIDAR sensor, and the spatial geometry of the detected vehicle, as reported in [25], [26]. Furthermore, utilizing communication to obtain orientation measurements also encounters challenges such as coordinate transformation and IMU accumulative errors. Compared with these approaches, our proposed method relies solely on local relative position measurements without requiring orientation measurements, improving feasibility, accuracy and reducing sensor costs.

There are a number of relevant works that address unicycle formation shape control without orientation measurement, which are similar to the problem considered in this paper. In [15], a general approach for the formation control of unicycle agents has been presented. Specifically, through the projection of the gradient-based formation control law to the direction of longitudinal and angular velocities, it has been demonstrated that a group of unicycle agents can reach the desired formation shape. However, the orientation consistency is not considered; the agents reach different headings without a potential extension for their motion control. In [27], a novel method for serial and parallel formation is proposed using local relative position measurements and real-time information on the leader's longitudinal and angular input velocities. However, the method is based on the leader-follower structure with a spanning tree, implying that variables will converge in a sequence. Particularly, the last followers encounter the problem with inconsistent distance constraints since the farther from the root agent, the longer it takes to converge to the desired distance.

This paper focuses on developing a distributed distance-based formation controller for unicycle agents without the need of orientation measurement. We propose a control law with an undirected graph that handles distance-based formation shape control and motion simultaneously. In particular, the agents must achieve a consensus on their orientation while converging to the desired shape, enabling them to move in unison, which could be considered as a significant extension of the work [15]. Furthermore, this paper builds upon our previous work [28], where interactions between agents are represented by an open-chain graph. In our new control approach, all agents are assumed to agree *a priori* on the desired eventual speed, but not on the orientation. There is no information on the desired velocity vector and the agents must reach a consensus on the common velocity vector. We require the measurements of relative positions and do not use relative orientations. Using recent progresses in the transversally exponential stability analysis, we prove the local exponential stability of the closed-loop system.

The outline of this paper is as follows. In Section II, we introduce the preliminaries and problem formulation. In

Section III, we propose the distance-based formation-motion control law for unicycle agents and analyse the asymptotic behavior of the closed-loop system. A simulation result is shown in Section IV. Finally, conclusions and future work are presented in Section V.

II. PRELIMINARIES & PROBLEM FORMULATION

A. Notation

For a given matrix $A \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$, we denote $\bar{A} = A \otimes I_m \in \mathbb{R}^{nm \times pm}$, where the symbol \otimes denotes the Kronecker product, and I_m is the m -dimensional identity matrix. For a given vector $z \in \mathbb{R}^m$, the diagonal matrix D_z is defined by $D_z = \text{diag}_{i=1, \dots, m}(z_i)$.

B. Graph

An undirected graph \mathbb{G} is defined by the tuple $(\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{E})$, where $\mathcal{V} = \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$ is the *vertex* set and $\mathcal{E} \subseteq \mathcal{V} \times \mathcal{V}$ is the *edge* set with $|\mathcal{E}|$ be the number of edges. The ordered pair $(i, j) \in \mathcal{E}$ refers to an edge in \mathcal{E} which is represented by an arrow with node i on its tail and node j on its head. We assume throughout the paper that there is no self-loop in \mathbb{G} , i.e., $(i, i) \notin \mathcal{E}$ for all $i \in \mathcal{V}$. The set of neighbors of vertex i is denoted by $\mathcal{N}_i \triangleq \{j \in \mathcal{V} \mid (i, j) \in \mathcal{E}\}$. Correspondingly, the set of edges associated to (i, \mathcal{N}_i) is denoted by $\mathcal{K}_i := \{k \mid (i, j) = \mathcal{E}_k \text{ for some } j \in \mathcal{N}_i\}$. We define the elements of the incidence matrix $B \in \mathbb{R}^{|\mathcal{V}| \times |\mathcal{E}|}$ of \mathbb{G} by

$$b_{ik} \triangleq \begin{cases} +1 & \text{if } i = \mathcal{E}_k^{\text{tail}} \\ -1 & \text{if } i = \mathcal{E}_k^{\text{head}} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where $\mathcal{E}_k^{\text{tail}}$ and $\mathcal{E}_k^{\text{head}}$ denote the tail and head nodes, respectively, of the edge \mathcal{E}_k , i.e., $\mathcal{E}_k = (\mathcal{E}_k^{\text{tail}}, \mathcal{E}_k^{\text{head}})$. The k -th column of B is denoted as b_k .

Given a finite collection of n points $\{p_i\}_{i=1}^n$ in \mathbb{R}^2 with $n \geq 2$, we define a *configuration* of \mathbb{G} by $p = [p_1^\top, \dots, p_n^\top]^\top \in \mathbb{R}^{2n}$, where $p_i \in \mathbb{R}^2$ represents the position of agent i . A framework in a 2D-plane, which is denoted by (\mathbb{G}, p) , is a combination of an undirected graph \mathbb{G} and a configuration p , i.e., every vertex $i \in \mathcal{V}$ is mapped to the point p_i in the configuration.

C. Infinitesimally rigid framework and distance-based rigid formations

Let us recall the notion of infinitesimally rigid framework in [1], [2] where desired formation shape based on the relative measurement is defined on the graph of multi-agent systems. A commonly used relative measurement is the relative displacement given by $z_{ij} = p_i - p_j$ for every $(i, j) \in \mathcal{E}$. For defining distance-based formation shape, an *edge* function is given by $f_{\mathbb{G}}(p) = \text{col}_{(i,j) \in \mathcal{E}}\{\|p_i - p_j\|\}$. Associated to $f_{\mathbb{G}}(p)$, the rigidity matrix $R(z)$ of the framework (\mathbb{G}, p) is defined by the Jacobian of the edge function $f_{\mathbb{G}}(p)$, which satisfies $R(z) = D_z^\top \bar{B}^\top$. For a given desired formation shape where the desired distance on every edge is given by $d = \text{col}_{(i,j) \in \mathcal{E}}\{\|z_{ij}^*\|\}$ with $\|z_{ij}^*\|$ be the desired distance

for edge (i, j) , the set of all equilibrium points that satisfy such distance constraint is $E := \{p | f_{\mathbb{G}}(p) = d\}$. For a given desired distance vector d , the corresponding desired framework (\mathbb{G}, p^*) with $p^* \in E$ is said to be *infinitesimally rigid* if the rank of $R(z^*)$ is $2|\mathcal{V}| - 3$ for 2D formation and $3|\mathcal{V}| - 6$ for 3D formation. For an infinitesimally rigid framework (\mathbb{G}, p^*) , the admissible infinitesimal displacement is translational and rotational motion [16].

We now briefly review the well-known analysis for single-integrator agents. Using the framework (\mathbb{G}, p) as defined before, it is assumed that each agent position p_i evolves in \mathbb{R}^d according to

$$\dot{p}_i = u_i$$

for all $i = 1, \dots, n$, where $u_i \in \mathbb{R}^d$ is the velocity control input. Using infinitesimally rigid framework, distributed distance-based formation control methods have been widely studied in the literature, see for example, [16], [29] and the references therein. In these works, the distance formation error in the k -th edge is defined by $e_k = \|z_k\|^l - d_k^l$ with $l \geq 1$ be any positive integer number. Associated to every edge k , the distributed control design method amounts to finding a positive definite function $V_k(e_k)$ so that the local gradient-based control law for each agent i is given by

$$u_i = - \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}_i} \frac{\partial V_k(e_k)}{\partial p_i}^\top.$$

Therefore, if we choose $V_k = \frac{1}{2} \|e_k\|^2$, one can obtain the closed-loop system dynamics of the whole system in the compact form

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{p} &= -\bar{B}D_z D_{\bar{z}} e = -R(z)^\top D_{\bar{z}} e \\ \dot{e} &= lD_{\bar{z}} D_z^\top \bar{B}^\top \dot{p} = -lD_{\bar{z}} R(z) R(z)^\top D_{\bar{z}} e, \end{aligned}$$

where $e, \bar{z} \in \mathbb{R}^{|\mathcal{E}|}$ are the stacked vectors of e_k 's and $\|z_k\|^{l-2}$'s respectively for all $k \in 1, \dots, |\mathcal{E}|$. The above distance-based formation control law guarantees exponential stability as studied in [16], [29].

D. Transversally Exponentially Stable Manifold

In this subsection, we introduce the concept of Transversally Exponential Stability which focuses on analyzing systems with an attractive invariant manifold rather than a specific equilibrium point.

Consider an autonomous system

$$\dot{e} = F(e, x), \quad \dot{x} = G(e, x), \quad (2)$$

where e is in \mathbb{R}^{n_e} , x is in \mathbb{R}^{n_x} and the function $F: \mathbb{R}^{n_e} \times \mathbb{R}^{n_x} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{n_e}$ and $G: \mathbb{R}^{n_e} \times \mathbb{R}^{n_x} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{n_x}$ are C^2 . The (unique) solution is denoted by $(E(e_0, x_0, t), X(e_0, x_0, t))$ which crosses (e_0, x_0) in $\mathbb{R}^{n_e} \times \mathbb{R}^{n_x}$ at $t = 0$. Without loss of generality, it is assumed that (2) is forward complete. In addition, We denote by $B_e(a)$ the open ball of radius a centered at the origin in \mathbb{R}^{n_e} . Let us recall the following result from [30] on the equivalence between transversal uniform local exponential stability (TULES-NL) and uniform exponential stability for the transversally linear system (UES-TL).

Definition 1: TULES-NL (Transversal uniform local exponential stability). For the system (2), there exist strictly positive real numbers r, k and λ such that, for all (e_0, x_0, t) in $B_e(r) \times \mathbb{R}^{n_x} \times \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$,

$$|E(e_0, x_0, t)| \leq k |e_0| \exp(-\lambda t).$$

Definition 2: UES-TL (Uniform exponential stability for the transversally linear system). The system

$$\dot{\tilde{x}} = \tilde{G}(\tilde{x}) := G(0, \tilde{x})$$

is forward complete and there exist strictly positive real numbers \tilde{k} and $\tilde{\lambda}$ such that any solution $(\tilde{E}(\tilde{e}_0, \tilde{x}_0, t), \tilde{X}(\tilde{x}_0, t))$ of the transversally linear system

$$\dot{\tilde{e}} = \frac{\partial F}{\partial e}(0, \tilde{x}) \tilde{e}, \quad \dot{\tilde{x}} = \tilde{G}(\tilde{x})$$

satisfies, for all $(\tilde{e}_0, \tilde{x}_0, t)$ in $\mathbb{R}^{n_e} \times \mathbb{R}^{n_x} \times \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$,

$$\left| \tilde{E}(\tilde{e}_0, \tilde{x}_0, t) \right| \leq \tilde{k} |\tilde{e}_0| \exp(-\tilde{\lambda} t).$$

Theorem 1 ([30]): The system (2) is TULES-NL if and only if it is UES-TL.

We remark that the global version of this theorem is presented in [31]. Because distance-based formation control typically deals with multiple equilibrium points, the global conditions in [31] cannot be fulfilled for general formation shape with n -agent systems.

E. Problem Formulation

In this paper, we consider unicycle agents, which are a class of nonholonomic systems and widely studied in literature. In particular, for each agent A_i with $i = 1, \dots, n$, its dynamics is given by

$$A_i : \begin{cases} \dot{x}_i = v_i \cos(\theta_i) \\ \dot{y}_i = v_i \sin(\theta_i) \\ \dot{\theta}_i = \omega_i, \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

where $v_i \in \mathbb{R}$ and $\omega_i \in \mathbb{R}$ are the speed (or longitudinal velocity) and angular velocity inputs, respectively; $p_i = \begin{bmatrix} x_i \\ y_i \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^2$ is the i -th agent position in the 2D plane and θ_i is its heading angle. For our control design and analysis, we define the unit vector of the unicycle heading $h_i \in \mathbb{R}^2$ and its orthonormal vector $h_i^\perp \in \mathbb{R}^2$ in the global coordinate frame by

$$h_i = \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\theta_i) \\ \sin(\theta_i) \end{bmatrix}, \quad h_i^\perp = \begin{bmatrix} -\sin(\theta_i) \\ \cos(\theta_i) \end{bmatrix}. \quad (4)$$

It is assumed that each agent can measure the relative position of a neighboring agent $j \in \mathcal{N}_i$ with respect to its own local reference frame. For simplicity of analysis and presentation, the interaction among agents is described by an undirected rigid graph \mathbb{G} .

Accordingly, the vectors $z_k \in \mathbb{R}^2$, $e_k \in \mathbb{R}$ and $e_k^\theta \in \mathbb{R}$ are introduced to represent the relative position vector, the distance error and the heading angular error, respectively, corresponding to the edge $\mathcal{E}_k = (i, j)$ and they are defined by

$$\left. \begin{aligned} z_k &:= p_i - p_j \\ e_k &:= \|z_k\|^2 - d_k^2 \\ e_k^\theta &:= \theta_i - \theta_j, \end{aligned} \right\}$$

where $d_k \in \mathbb{R}$ is the desired distance between agent i and agent j in edge \mathcal{E}_k . Additionally, the stacked vector of the sensed relative position by the agents can be described by

$$z = \bar{B}^\top p. \quad (5)$$

The objective of this paper is to develop a control law that allows agents to maintain an equal velocity with speed v^* while preserving distance-based rigid formation shape and orientation consensus. The main advantage of our control law is that it eliminates the need for orientation measurements among neighbors as it is usual in current studies [23], [24].

Distributed formation control problem of unicycle agents with velocity agreement: For an infinitesimally rigid framework (\mathbb{G}, p) linked to a set of unicycles with dynamics (3), we aim to design a distributed control law for all the unicycles such that $\begin{bmatrix} e_k(t) \\ e_k^\theta(t) \end{bmatrix} \rightarrow 0$ as $t \rightarrow \infty$ for all $\mathcal{E}_k \in \mathcal{E}$, without requiring relative orientation measurements.

III. DISTRIBUTED FORMATION-MOTION CONTROL OF UNICYCLES

To accommodate the design of our distributed controller, we consider the dynamics of a kinematic (offset) point located in front of the agent, which is defined by

$$p_{ir} = p_i + r h_i,$$

where h_i is the unicycle heading vector as in (4) and r is the distance between the pivoting point of the unicycle and the offset point. For these kinematic offset points, the errors between i -th agent and j -th agent are defined by

$$\begin{aligned} e_{kr} &:= \|z_{ir}\|^2 - d_k^2 \\ e_{kr}^\theta &:= \theta_i - \theta_j, \end{aligned}$$

where $z_{kr} = p_{ir} - p_{jr}$. For simplifying the stability analysis later, the first order distance error is given by $\bar{e}_{kr} = \|z_{kr}\| - d_k$. The relationship between the error variables e_{kr} and \bar{e}_{kr} satisfies

$$e_{kr} = \bar{e}_{kr}^2 + 2d_k \bar{e}_{kr}. \quad (6)$$

A. Distributed control law

Applying the combination of the distance-based formation gradient control input and v^* input in the heading direction, the dynamics of kinematic offset points satisfy

$$\dot{p}_{ir} = - \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}_i} b_{ik} z_{kr} e_{kr} + v^* h_i,$$

Using the kinematic offset points, we develop the distributed control law where the inputs are decomposed into the longitudinal velocity input (e.g., the velocity in the agent's direction) and the tangential velocity input (orthogonal to the longitudinal one). Thus, the distributed control law for agents A_i , $i = 1, \dots, n$ is given by

$$\begin{aligned} v_i &= h_i^\top \dot{p}_{ir} = -h_i^\top \left\{ \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}_i} b_{ik} z_{kr} e_{kr} \right\} + v^* \\ \omega_i &= \frac{1}{r} (h_i^\perp)^\top \dot{p}_{ir} = -\frac{1}{r} (h_i^\perp)^\top \left\{ \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}_i} b_{ik} z_{kr} e_{kr} \right\}. \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

where b_{ik} is the element of incidence matrix in (1).

B. Stability analysis

In this subsection, we analyse the stability of the closed-loop system consisting of the n -agent unicycle (3) team with the control law (7).

Firstly, let us consider two unicycle agents A_i and A_j which form the edge \mathcal{E}_k and are controlled by (7). By denoting $z_{kr} = \begin{bmatrix} x_{kr} \\ y_{kr} \end{bmatrix}$, the angle $\varphi_{kr} := \tan^{-1}(\frac{y_{kr}}{x_{kr}})$ defines the angle of z_{kr} with respect to the local reference frame of A_i and the vector φ_r is the stacked vector of φ_{kr} for all $k \in \{1, \dots, |\mathcal{E}|\}$. In addition, we define the matrix $S_k = \begin{bmatrix} \sin(\varphi_{1r} - \varphi_{kr}) & & \\ & \ddots & \\ & & \sin(\varphi_{mr} - \varphi_{kr}) \end{bmatrix}$ for all $k \in \{1, \dots, |\mathcal{E}|\}$. Using $\bar{e}_{kr}, e_{kr}^\theta, \varphi_{kr}$, the closed-loop system dynamics of the k -th edge is given by

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \dot{\bar{e}}_{kr} &= \frac{z_{kr}^\top \dot{z}_{kr}}{\|z_{kr}\|} = \frac{z_{kr}^\top}{\|z_{kr}\|} \left(-\bar{b}_k^\top \bar{B} D_{z_r} e_r + v^* \bar{b}_k^\top h \right) \\ \dot{e}_{kr}^\theta &= -\frac{1}{r} \bar{b}_k^\top D_{(h^\perp)^\top} \bar{B} D_{z_r} e_r \\ \dot{\varphi}_{kr} &= -\frac{\bar{b}_k^\top B D_{\tilde{z}}^{-1} S_k e_r}{\|z_{kr}\|} \\ &\quad + \frac{v^* [\sin(\theta_i - \varphi_{kr}) - \sin(\theta_i - \varphi_{kr} - e_{kr}^\theta)]}{\|z_{kr}\|} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (8)$$

where \tilde{z} is the stacked vectors of $\|z_{kr}\|^{-1}$ for all $k \in 1, \dots, |\mathcal{E}|$.

Based on the analysis of (8), we identify two equilibrium points within the closed-loop system. The first one corresponds to $\bar{e}_{kr} = 0, e_{kr}^\theta = 0, \dot{\varphi}_{kr} = 0$, representing agents achieving and maintaining the desired formation with a constant consensus velocity. The second equilibrium point involves $\dot{\bar{e}}_{kr} = 0, \dot{e}_{kr}^\theta = 0, \dot{\varphi}_{kr} = 0$, along with $\bar{e}_{kr} \neq 0, e_{kr}^\theta \neq 0$ indicating agents reaching and maintaining an undesired stable rotating formation. The first equilibrium corresponds to the case where the agents are in the desired formation shape.

In the following, we will use Theorem 1 for establishing the local exponential stability of the desired formation shape. Following the notation of Theorem 1 in (2), we define $x := \begin{bmatrix} \bar{e}_r \\ \varphi_r \end{bmatrix}$ and $e = \bar{e}_r$. Correspondingly, the closed-loop system (8) can be expressed into the form of (2) with appropriate F and G as follows

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\bar{e}}_r &= F \left(\bar{e}_r, \begin{bmatrix} e_r^\theta \\ \varphi_r \end{bmatrix} \right) \\ \begin{bmatrix} \dot{e}_r^\theta \\ \dot{\varphi}_r \end{bmatrix} &= G \left(\bar{e}_r, \begin{bmatrix} e_r^\theta \\ \varphi_r \end{bmatrix} \right), \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

where F and G are the compact forms of the dynamics expressed in (8).

Proposition 1: Consider the closed-loop system (9) with graph \mathbb{G} driven by the inputs (7). If the formation in the desired shape $\{\bar{e}_r = 0\}$ is infinitesimally and minimally rigid, then the system is transversally uniformly locally exponentially stable at the manifold

$$\mathcal{H} = \left\{ \left(\bar{e}_r, \begin{bmatrix} e_r^\theta \\ \varphi_r \end{bmatrix} \right) \mid \bar{e}_r = 0, G \left(0, \begin{bmatrix} e_r^\theta \\ \varphi_r \end{bmatrix} \right) = 0 \right\}.$$

PROOF. The proof of the proposition will be based on Theorem 1. Particularly, we will firstly show that the corresponding autonomous systems of (9) is TULES-NL, or equivalently, it

is UES-TL. For the latter case, the transversal linear system is given by

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \dot{\bar{e}}_r &= \frac{\partial F}{\partial \bar{e}_r} \left(0, \begin{bmatrix} \bar{e}_r^\theta \\ \bar{\varphi}_r \end{bmatrix} \right) \tilde{e}_r \\ \begin{bmatrix} \dot{\bar{e}}_r \\ \dot{\bar{\varphi}}_r \end{bmatrix} &= \tilde{G} \left(\begin{bmatrix} \bar{e}_r^\theta \\ \bar{\varphi}_r \end{bmatrix} \right), \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (10)$$

where $\tilde{G} \left(\begin{bmatrix} \bar{e}_r^\theta \\ \bar{\varphi}_r \end{bmatrix} \right) := G \left(0, \begin{bmatrix} \bar{e}_r^\theta \\ \bar{\varphi}_r \end{bmatrix} \right)$. By the form of G in (8), it follows that

$$\begin{bmatrix} \dot{\bar{e}}_{kr} \\ \dot{\bar{\varphi}}_{kr} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ \frac{v^* [\sin(\theta_i - \bar{\varphi}_{kr}) - \sin(\theta_i - \bar{\varphi}_{kr} - \bar{e}_{kr}^\theta)]}{\|z_{kr}\|} \end{bmatrix} \quad (11)$$

for all $k \in 1, \dots, |\mathcal{E}|$. By the definition of z_{kr} , the variable $\|z_{kr}\|$ is constant when $e_r = 0$. Thus, the state equation (11) is forward complete since the right-hand side of (11) is bounded.

We will prove now the stability property of (10) in the neighborhood of the equilibrium point $\tilde{e}_r = 0$ (i.e. UES-TL property holds). Using F as in (9), its variational form as in (10) is given by

$$\frac{\partial F}{\partial \bar{e}_r} \left(0, \begin{bmatrix} \bar{e}_r^\theta \\ \bar{\varphi}_r \end{bmatrix} \right) = \frac{\partial}{\partial \bar{e}_r} \left(-D_{\bar{z}} D_{z_r}^\top \bar{B}^\top \bar{B} D_{z_r} e_r + v^* D_{\bar{z}} D_{z_r}^\top \bar{B}^\top h \right) \Big|_{\bar{e}_r=0}. \quad (12)$$

Since the term $v^* D_{\bar{z}} D_{z_r}^\top \bar{B}^\top h$ above is independent to \bar{e}_r ,

$$\frac{\partial F}{\partial \bar{e}_r} \left(0, \begin{bmatrix} \bar{e}_r^\theta \\ \bar{\varphi}_r \end{bmatrix} \right) = \frac{\partial}{\partial \bar{e}_r} \left(-D_{\bar{z}} D_{z_r}^\top \bar{B}^\top \bar{B} D_{z_r} e_r \right) \Big|_{\bar{e}_r=0}.$$

One can observe that the resulting variational system (10) with the above $\frac{\partial F}{\partial \bar{e}_r}$ is also the variational system of the following autonomous system

$$\dot{\bar{e}}_r = -D_{\bar{z}} D_{z_r}^\top \bar{B}^\top \bar{B} D_{z_r} e_r \quad (13)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} \dot{\bar{e}}_r \\ \dot{\bar{\varphi}}_r \end{bmatrix} = G \left(\bar{e}_r, \begin{bmatrix} \bar{e}_r^\theta \\ \bar{\varphi}_r \end{bmatrix} \right), \quad (14)$$

where G is the same as the one given in (9). By the equivalence relation from Theorem 1, it follows that the UES-TL of (10) is equivalent to TULES-NL of (13)-(14).

According to the definition of TULES-NL in Section II-C, the TULES-NL of (13)-(14) is only related to the solution $\bar{E} \left(\bar{e}_0, \begin{bmatrix} \bar{e}_{r0}^\theta \\ \bar{\varphi}_{r0} \end{bmatrix}, t \right)$ of (13). Let us consider $V(e_r) = \frac{1}{4} \|e_r\|^2$ as a candidate Lyapunov function for (13). Recalling the relationship between \bar{e}_r and e_r in (6), the function V is also a positive definite function of \bar{e}_r . Using $\dot{e}_r = 2D_{\bar{z}}^{-1} \dot{\bar{e}}_r$, the time-derivative of V is given by

$$\dot{V} = -e_r^\top D_{z_r}^\top \bar{B}^\top \bar{B} D_{z_r} e_r.$$

By the hypothesis of the proposition, where the framework (\mathbb{G}, p^*) is infinitesimally rigid, the matrix

$$Q(\bar{e}_r) = D_{z_r}^\top \bar{B}^\top \bar{B} D_{z_r}$$

is positive definite at the desired formation shape, since $D_{z_r}^\top \bar{B}^\top$ has full row rank at $\bar{e}_r = 0$. Because the eigenvalues of $Q(\bar{e}_r)$ are smooth functions of \bar{e}_r , there exists a compact set

$$\mathcal{Q} \triangleq \{\bar{e}_r \mid \|\bar{e}_r\|^2 \leq \rho\}$$

for some positive constant ρ where $Q(\bar{e}_r)$ is positive definite. Define λ_{\min} to be the smallest eigenvalue of $Q(\bar{e}_r)$ in \mathcal{Q} . Then

$$\dot{V} \leq -\lambda_{\min} \|e_r\|^2 = -\lambda_{\min} \sum_{k=1}^{|\mathcal{E}|} \bar{e}_{kr}^2 (\bar{e}_{kr} + 2d_k)^2,$$

which immediately implies the local exponential convergence of \bar{e}_r to zeros. This implies that for (13) there exist strictly positive real numbers k and λ such that for all $(\bar{e}_0, \begin{bmatrix} \bar{e}_{r0}^\theta \\ \bar{\varphi}_{r0} \end{bmatrix}, t)$ in $B_e(r) \times \mathbb{R}^{n_x} \times \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$,

$$\left| E \left(\bar{e}_0, \begin{bmatrix} \bar{e}_{r0}^\theta \\ \bar{\varphi}_{r0} \end{bmatrix}, t \right) \right| \leq k \exp(-\lambda t) |\bar{e}_0|$$

holds. It implies that (13)-(14) is TULES-NL. By invoking Theorem 1, we conclude the transversally linear system (10) is UES-TL and the original closed-loop system (8) is TULES-NL according to Theorem 1. \square

Remark 1: Since system (8) presents an attractive invariant manifold, rather than an equilibrium point, the classical exponential stability analysis cannot be applied immediately. The recent work on Transversally Exponential Stability allows us to study the exponential stability towards such invariant manifold simply by analyzing the linearized sub-system that is ‘‘transversal’’ to the manifold, without the need for a stability analysis for time-varying systems, where the dynamics of the transversal system can be considered as an exogenous signal to the error sub-system. Note that the recent global transversal exponential stability result in [31] cannot be applied directly in this case as it requires strong assumptions that are not satisfied by system (8).

Proposition 1 shows that the multi-agent unicycle systems can form and maintain a desired shape using the distributed control law (7). For analyzing the resulting motion coordination due to the introduction of a constant velocity input v^* , the convergence of heading angle errors need to be taken into account. Let us define $e_a := \begin{bmatrix} \bar{e}_r \\ \bar{e}_r^\theta \end{bmatrix}$ and rewrite the system (9) as

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{e}_a &= H(e_a, \varphi_r), \\ \dot{\varphi}_r &= I(e_a, \varphi_r), \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

where H and I are the corresponding functions in (2), respectively. In order to establish the orientation consensus, we introduce a new manifold containing both the distance errors and heading angle errors as follows

$$\mathcal{H}_r = \{(e_a, \varphi_r) \mid e_a = 0, I(0, \varphi_r) = 0\}.$$

It is clear that the multi-unicycle systems can achieve desired shape formation and orientation consensus if and only if \mathcal{H} and \mathcal{H}_r are equivalent.

Proposition 2: The manifolds \mathcal{H} and \mathcal{H}_r are equivalent.

PROOF.

It is obvious that $\mathcal{H}_r \subset \mathcal{H}$. From the closed-loop system’s equation (8), when $\bar{e}_r = 0$ and $\dot{\bar{e}}_r = 0$, it fol-

lows that $\begin{bmatrix} \cos(\theta_1 - \varphi_{1r}) \\ \vdots \\ \cos(\theta_i - \varphi_{kr}) \\ \vdots \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\theta_2 - \varphi_{1r}) \\ \vdots \\ \cos(\theta_j - \varphi_{kr}) \\ \vdots \end{bmatrix}$. Correspondingly,

since $G(0, X) = 0$, we also have that $\begin{bmatrix} \sin(\theta_1 - \varphi_{1r}) \\ \vdots \\ \sin(\theta_i - \varphi_{kr}) \\ \vdots \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \sin(\theta_2 - \varphi_{1r}) \\ \vdots \\ \sin(\theta_j - \varphi_{kr}) \\ \vdots \end{bmatrix}$. These two equations imply that $e_r^\theta = 0$. Hence we can deduce that $\mathcal{H}_r \subset \mathcal{H}$. \square

Based on Propositions 1 and 2, we can conclude that the system (15) is locally exponentially stable with respect to the manifold $\mathcal{H}_r = \{(e_a, \varphi_r) | e_a = 0, I(0, \varphi_r) = 0\}$. Based on the motion equation (7), the speed of all agents is v^* in this manifold. Therefore, the distributed control law (7) enables the multi-unicycle agents to attain the desired formation shape and maintain a constant reference speed v^* at the same orientation. Moreover, in real applications, it can be more convenient to determine the alignment of the orientations by only checking the inter-agent distance errors.

IV. NUMERICAL SIMULATIONS

A. Simulation setup

For the simulation setup, we consider an *infinitesimally rigid* formation of four unicycles. In this case, the incidence matrix B of the multi-unicycle system is given by

$$B = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & -1 & 0 & -1 \\ -1 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 1 & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (16)$$

For the first setup, the four agents are randomly initialized at

$$\begin{aligned} p_1(0) &= \begin{bmatrix} 6 \\ 22 \end{bmatrix}, & p_2(0) &= \begin{bmatrix} 15 \\ 5 \end{bmatrix}, \\ p_3(0) &= \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ -3 \end{bmatrix}, & p_4(0) &= \begin{bmatrix} 6 \\ -6 \end{bmatrix}, \end{aligned}$$

and the initial heading angles are $\{\theta_1(0) = 0, \theta_2(0) = -\frac{\pi}{6}, \theta_3(0) = -\pi, \theta_4(0) = \frac{\pi}{3}\}$. The reference speed is randomly set as $v^* = 2$. For the target formation shape, the desired distance set of edges is set as $\{d_1 = 8, d_2 = 8, d_3 = 8, d_4 = 8, d_5 = 8\sqrt{2}\}$, which corresponds to a square with side length of 8.

In the second setup, a Monte Carlo simulation is performed to analyze statistically the performance of the proposed distributed control law. Due to the local result as established in Proposition 1, the Monte Carlo simulation can reveal the efficacy of our method under various simulation conditions. Following the Monte Carlo simulation setup as used in [32], we generate 1000 numerical simulation results with the following setup: 1) for each simulation, the number of agents is 4, and the incidence matrix is given by (16); 2) the initial position of agent i , $p_i^0 = \begin{bmatrix} x_i^0 \\ y_i^0 \end{bmatrix}$, is sampled from a uniform distribution on $[-40, 40] \times [-40, 40]$; 3) the desired distance between neighboring agents, d_i , $i \in 1, \dots, |\mathcal{E}|$, is sampled from a uniform distribution on the interval $[3, 10]$; and 4) the initial speed is sampled from a uniform distribution on the interval $[10, 20]$.

B. Simulation results

For the first simulation setup, the trajectories of unicycle agents with the proposed distributed control law are shown in Figure 1 where the agents are moving in the 2D-plane (x, y) . In this figure, multi-unicycle agents are able to maintain the desired square formation shape while moving in the same direction in unison. The distance error of edges, the trajectory of agents' heading angle and speed are presented in Figures 2 to 4, respectively. It can be seen in the figures that all distance errors converge to zero and their heading angle and speed converge to the same value.

For the Monte-Carlo simulation results, we use $e = \begin{bmatrix} e_d \\ e_\theta \end{bmatrix}$ to represent the total error, where e_d is the distance error between neighboring agents and e_θ is the heading angle error between neighboring agents. Figure 5 shows the statistics of the norm of error $\|e(t)\|$ for the 75% confidence interval and for all data (100%). We highlight that the boundary of data illustrate discontinuity due to our definition for orientation within the interval $(-\pi, \pi]$. In Figure 5, it can be seen that the mean of $\|e(t)\|$ asymptotically converges to 0 and the majority of the samples that are within the 75% confidence interval also converge to zero. The Monte Carlo simulation results show also there are initial conditions that lead to the convergence to an undesired equilibrium point as pointed out in Section III-B. Even though we prove only the local exponential stability of the desired formation manifold in Proposition 1, the Monte Carlo simulation results show that the proposed method is still effective in a larger domain than the neighborhood of \mathcal{H}_r .

Fig. 1: Trajectories for four unicycle agents with the distributed formation control; (■, ■, ■, ■, ■) = (A1, A2, A3, A4, Final edges).

V. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we have proposed a distance-based distributed formation-motion control law for unicycle agents. Using recent results in transversal uniform exponential stability, we establish the local exponential convergence of the unicycle agents to the desired rigid formation where all agents move together at a constant reference speed. The simulation results validate numerically our main results using four unicycle agents. Given

Fig. 2: The plot of distance error of four unicycle systems in the numerical simulation of the distributed formation control.

Fig. 3: The plot of heading angle of four unicycle systems in the numerical simulation of the distributed formation control.

Fig. 4: The plot of speed of four unicycle systems in the numerical simulation of the distributed formation control.

Fig. 5: Statistics of the norm of error e with 75% confidence interval (shown in blue area) and all (100%) data (shown in red area).

the local exponential stability of the closed-loop systems, our proposed method offers robustness against small perturbation to the longitudinal and angular input velocities. This lays the basis for our future works, where collision avoidance and steering the group motion can be achieved by considering a reference governor for the reference speed and reference angular velocity.

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